

CREATING GREEN JOBS AMONG SCHOOL STUDENTS: THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL LITERACY, GREEN SKILLS, AND GREEN BEHAVIOUR IN WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Climate change and environmental degradation have become urgent global issues. In addition, the impacts have affected welfare in the economic and social fields. In this context, an effort is needed to support the transition to a green economy by creating green jobs among school students. However, there is still a knowledge gap in its implementation, especially in understanding how environmental literacy, green skills, and behavior can affect green jobs. This study will use a quantitative approach using a survey involving high school students, where data will be collected through a questionnaire based on a Likert scale. The main results of this study indicate that green jobs through workforce development influence improving environmental literacy, green skills, and green behavior. The results of the analysis in the study showed that Workforce Development contributed to Environmental Literacy with an influence value of 0.194 ($p < 0.05$), Green Skills 0.201 ($p < 0.001$), and Green Behavior 0.254 ($p < 0.001$). Based on these results, it is proven that investing in workforce development is the right step in supporting green job creation efforts, making contributions to environmental sustainability, and improving the workforce in the future.

Index Terms: Green Jobs, Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, Green Behaviour, Workforce Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change and environmental degradation have led to devastating disasters for millions of people, making them a serious concern in various parts of the world [1].

Extreme climate change could worsen the decline in global health in the coming decades, especially those caused by human activities, one of which is the effect of greenhouse gases that can cause climate change and extreme weather. Climate change can trigger major disasters such as droughts, floods, storms, and rising sea levels [2]. In the long term, climate change disrupts ecological systems and causes the distribution of disease sources to be more vulnerable to attacking the poor and vulnerable [3]. Drought disasters due to climate change can cause crop failures and livestock deaths that occur in various regions, triggering hunger for residents [4]. Climate change causes significant economic impacts, including threats to income sources due to drought and crop failure [4]. In addition, challenges in the distribution of goods are influenced by rising fuel prices and the transition to more sustainable business processes [5]. The implications of political instability shocks on food security risks and distribution can lead to inter-community and geopolitical conflicts [6]. The issue of climate change requires collaborative action from various sectors to protect ecosystems that continue to be threatened. Cross-sectoral cooperation is essential to prevent further crises and to create a sustainable future for society.

The creation of Green Jobs is the answer to efforts to reduce the impact of climate change. Green Jobs are oriented towards making a positive contribution to the restoration of the state of the environment [7]. Green Jobs comprise various sectors with good prospects, namely renewable energy, green technology, waste treatment, and infrastructure development with sustainability concepts [8]. Green Jobs is a priority sector that encourages the creation of decent jobs and cares for the environment, following the ILO and the United Nations description. Green Jobs and sustainability are catalysts for supporting technological change, circular economic growth, and strategic bioeconomy [9]. Environmental policy practices can spur the adoption of workforce needs that must be aligned with changes toward productive and sustainable development models. Green Jobs have more excellent prospects in the future because they play a role in developing environmentally friendly technology innovations in agriculture, architecture, transportation, and energy [10]. The government and industry are starting to open the field of Green Jobs to overcome environmental challenges and achieve profitability in the future [11]. The development of Green Jobs, of course, requires knowledge of good Environmental Literacy.

Green Jobs are not just a job demand in the professional world but can be a personal lifestyle in fostering environmental awareness [12]. The practice of Green Jobs is also influenced by the understanding of the concept of Environmental Literacy by employees who work in environmentally friendly industries [13]. Environmental literacy includes understanding concepts, attitudes, and sensitivity in solving problems. Proper Environmental Literacy Planning will greatly contribute to individual decision-making decisions and actions that care about the environment [14]. Environmental literacy includes cognitive knowledge, ecological behavior, and environmental values. Sustainable goals are widely promoted in supporting Environmental Literacy actions to encourage proactive actions and commitment to environmental conservation efforts [15].

The development of environmental literacy is a form of individuals responsible for environmental problems so that they can grow their green skills.

Green Skills includes technical and non-technical aspects in implementing environmentally friendly attitudes in the workplace. The environment-friendly skills gap among workers can slow down performance in the sustainable industry sector [16]. Periodic changes in the work system change the duties and roles of employees in carrying out activities, so prospective employees are always required to develop new skills, one of which is Green Skills [17]. Workers contribute to creating operational efficiency and a work environment responsible for the ecosystem. Workers' skills continue to develop work practices that align with evolving green environmental regulatory policies [18]. Green skills are reflected in daily professional tasks and individual behaviors that protect the environment.

Green Behaviour as a proactive approach to improving environmental sustainability and solving environmental problems. Each individual takes concrete actions to preserve the ecosystem by implementing Green Behaviour [19]. Sustainability programs through significant strategic management are supported by employees who have Green Behaviour [20]. In environmentally friendly practices, obstacles often arise related to company performance standards. Pro-environmental behavior can improve the quality of life and environmental awareness professionally and individually in the work environment [21]. Supervision from the company also needs to be carried out to ensure that activities are carried out, especially if they are not included in the job's main duties. This is to show that commitment to the environment is truly implemented. Green behavior is also reflected in consuming environmentally friendly labeled products and supporting local MSME products [22].

However, the Green Jobs concept is still not being used, and companies and prospective workers widely know it. Prospective workers have not fully mastered the understanding of Environmental Literacy, so the existing understanding is quite diverse, especially in interpreting environmental issues in the world of work [23]. In addition, Green Skills have not been widely introduced to prospective workers in formal schools or job training centers. Prospective workers do not have enough provisions to align themselves with the demands of an industry that implements sustainability aspects in every activity [24]. The lack of Environmental Literacy and environmentally friendly appearance is reflected in environmentally friendly behavior in the workplace. Green behavior must be accumulated collectively to create a sustainable work ecosystem [25]. Knowledge and prospects related to Green Jobs have not been widely taught among school students, so many students are more interested in choosing careers in conventional fields. Therefore, early introduction to green jobs is crucial to equip students with the understanding and skills to face environmental challenges.

The younger generation in schools needs more in-depth education related to Green Workforce Development. This is to provide provisions to contribute to green and sustainable economic development. Green Workforce Development can be integrated with the learning process in schools, providing more enrichment related to environmental

issues, digital skills, and job prospects in sustainable industries to increase their knowledge of green workforce. In addition, the training program can open students' insights into understanding Green Jobs. Green Workforce Development is carried out by instilling values of environmental concern, natural resource management, and the application of green technology in innovative work sectors. The introduction to career proposals can motivate students to actively contribute to preparing for their future dreams of entering an environmentally friendly world of work. Green Jobs education from schools is expected to create an environmentally friendly workforce and green economic growth in Indonesia.

The purpose of this study is to review the influence of Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behaviour on the creation of Green Jobs among school students. Workforce Development has a role in moderating the relationship between the variables raised. The existing research aims to explore research related to Green Jobs among school students more deeply. Workforce development consists of training and learning about sustainable green jobs. The urgency of this research can create a forum for students to know and understand Green Jobs to support awareness related to the environmental crisis and green economic transition [26]. Environmentally friendly Workforce Development will provide skills and knowledge in facing challenges and taking opportunities in a sustainable workplace ecosystem [27]. Workforce Development supports the adoption of technology in the industrial world and reduces negativity in running business operations that will arise [28]. In addition, workforce development is expected to help overcome the labor market's skills shortage and create new jobs supporting economic growth and social sustainability.

2. BACKGROUND OF THEORIES AND HYPOTHESES

2.1 Implementation of Green Jobs in Companies

Implementing Green Jobs through policies made by the company ensures that business operations run well and support aspects of business sustainability. Environmental impact assessments conducted by companies can identify the implementation of environmentally friendly policies among employees [29]. The company encourages environmentally friendly practices through incentives and regular training. Companies can reduce energy use and waste disposal costs and support government policies toward a green economic transition [30]. Evaluation and reporting of the performance of the implementation of Green Jobs will be used as a reference to determine actions and improvements in preparing commitments. Using environmentally friendly procedures in business processes can optimize company profits [26]. Four important indicators raised in implementing Green Jobs include the quality of the work environment, gender equality, career sustainability, and work culture. The quality of the work environment is one indicator that influences the foundation that supports Green Jobs. In addition, a good work environment can also support worker comfort in carrying out programs following environmentally friendly practices [31]. Environmental quality, including the air's state, impacts employees' psychological and physical health in carrying out office activities [32]. In addition, the institutional environment at work can positively encourage environmentally

friendly economic development. The institutional environment includes many aspects, such as the market environment, which has the potential to play essential roles in business regulations [33]. In addition, gender equality is necessary to ensure equal opportunities for all employees. Every employee of the male or female gender has equal participation in determining the chosen career path [34]. Employees have equal access to training and job opportunities in the job promotion process. The low involvement of women creates a misconception about the low ability of women in business management compared to men [35]. The existing misconception began to be broken by a policy of empowering women to increase equality in running a business, especially in the green industry. Gender equality in green economy development significantly impacts sustainable industrial growth globally [36].

Career sustainability in Green Jobs is an excellent opportunity for prospective workers to enter this field. Long-term career planning for prospective workers determines the future direction through appropriate career guidance [37]. Career sustainability shows a pattern over time about a sequence of career experiences within a particular social sphere. The career ecosystem also encourages aspects of career sustainability by creating dependencies between company employees [38]. The elements of people, context, and time greatly influence the career sustainability of each individual. Career sustainability management is dynamic and supported by influencing colleagues, non-employment factors, and employers [39]. The fourth indicator of Green Jobs is work culture. Work culture is a collective value that is applied to behavior patterns in the company. Developing a positive work culture in the company can foster employees' sense of ownership towards work and build a solid commitment to implementing the concept of sustainability [40]. Employees' views on the company's perception are greatly influenced by the work culture that has been in place, so it triggers the attraction and retention of employees at work, including job satisfaction [41]. Based on the above arguments, we propose that:

H1. Green Jobs have a positive and significant effect on Environmental Literacy

H2. Green Jobs have a positive and significant effect on Green Skills

H3. Green Jobs have a positive and significant effect on Green Behavior

2.2 Environmental Literacy Levels among Industrial Workers

Environmental literacy can be understood as appropriate actions to maintain environmental health or restore the health of the environment that has been damaged. Environmental literacy is an interaction between humans and the environment that involves various sciences [13]. Previous studies have looked at the interaction between students and teachers in environmental learning to provide an understanding of Environmental Literacy from an early age. Environmental literacy includes the development of each individual's morality, ethics, and motivation [42]. Environmental literacy is critical because it can have a direct impact, one of which is on aspects of community consumption that are more likely to start adopting green consumption behavior. The level of consumption of green and sustainable labeled products is greatly

influenced by high environmental literacy, so more attention is paid to the impact of product use on the environment [12]. Environmental literacy among workers is also critical because it will significantly impact the company's sense of responsibility and performance. Therefore, investing in Environmental Literacy is a strategic step in creating a cleaner, more efficient, and more sustainable industry [43].

Three essential indicators that include environmental literacy are to be explored: environmental values, environmental responsibility, and perception of environmental problems. The environmental values owned by workers result in a high commitment to actively implementing and supporting the company's efforts to reduce environmental pollution [44]. The existing values are related to the beliefs and principles of each individual to preserve the environment. Existing theories show that humans and the environment have a strong affinity based on a value orientation towards the environment [45]. Environmental values will be included in pro-environmental actions that can be normalized because every worker has a moral obligation to act to protect the environment. These values shape worker morals that align with the company's sustainability goals so that employees change in the work environment [46]. Environmental responsibility is the awareness and commitment of prospective workers to implementing environmentally friendly practices. Companies are at the forefront of building a green economy through environmental responsibility [47]. The relevant institutions are responsible for achieving sustainable goals and visions for the environment. The government actively provides regulations to strengthen environmental policies and management. Environmental responsibility is a concrete step in promoting environmental management and governance [48]. Companies must develop an environmental foundation for incentive mechanisms to motivate employees to grow their responsibility towards the environment. They have increased environmental responsibility within the company to enhance the role of employees in supporting the set environmental targets [49].

Perception of environmental problems can provide information about responses to environmental issues in implementing activity procedures. The perception possessed by workers can provide actions that adopt green and sustainable practices in the work they are engaged in [50]. Every individual perceives problems that are influenced by personal factors and cultural elements. Differences greatly influence attitudes in beliefs, life experiences, socio-culture, government policies, consumption practices, and environmental assessments [51]. In addition, the digital space and policies provide an overview in forming decisions oriented to environmental issues. Companies with a high commitment to the environment will strengthen the perception of environmental problems in every regulation [52]. Workers with good perceptions of environmental issues will be more responsive to the need to adopt more sustainable practices [53]. Applying environmental literacy through these three indicators will help create a more environmentally conscious work environment. Based on the arguments above, we propose that:

H4. Workforce Development has a positive and significant effect on Environmental Literacy

2.3 The Need for Green Skills in the Green Economy Sector

Green skills are important in supporting the green economy sector transition program and building global awareness of sustainability. The green sector provides development in agriculture, energy, and environmentally friendly construction. Good employee skills can optimize operational activities and drive innovation in green technology [54]. Green skills are new skills needed to carry out green and non-hijua jobs. A high level of analytical and operational knowledge is the assumption behind the growth of Green Skills [55]. Green Skills includes design, model development, production processes, and technology control in the industry. Green Skills supports a just transition process in developing a low-carbon energy industry in the United Kingdom. These skills include the ability to integrate environmental principles into everyday practice in the workplace [56].

Green Skills encompasses four main aspects: idea and knowledge management, developing driving strategies, and innovative sustainability, as well as sustainable, innovative energy management. Idea knowledge management is part of developing new ideas to reduce the impact of environmental damage in the manufacturing industry—knowledge management is a resource for producing a quality workforce [57]. Several companies have widely adopted ideas and know-how management, implementing knowledge management as part of their evolution in achieving their goals. Employee performance can be monitored through knowledge management in shaping a culture of innovation that continues to grow [58].

Practical knowledge and idea management can regularly create alternative solutions to solve problems in the company and support long-term business sustainability [59]. The second indicator is the development of green strategies in the company. Green strategies can drive companies to create green innovations and support sustainable processes [60]. The company's green strategy has had a significant impact on increasing the company's green income in the pilot process in China. Employees with skills in managing strategies will greatly support the rare steps to proactively reduce the carbon footprint in the company [61]. These strategies are the foundation for the company's transformation towards more sustainable operations.

Sustainable innovation can adopt the use of green technology in industrial development. Companies can develop environmentally friendly products that users increasingly demand [62]. Sustainable innovation supports the circular economy concept because it can minimize waste and environmental pollution. Eco-friendly products will further direct substantial financial, social, and environmental use and create conditions conducive to sustainable products [63]. Innovation in sustainability in companies is crucial to remain competitive while fulfilling social and environmental responsibilities. Innovation management can consider the value of an environment-based economy that is more profitable. Energy usage management in the workplace can control energy consumption among employees and companies.

The contribution of energy management efficiency within the scope of an integrated framework increases the production of sustainable green energy [64]. Efficient use of energy can reduce energy consumption and reduce operational costs. With effective

energy management, companies can reduce environmental impact while improving financial performance [65]. Green Skills includes all four indicators to ensure they comply with environmental regulations and become leaders in sustainable business practices. Based on the above arguments, we propose that:

H5. Green Jobs have a positive and significant effect on Green Skills.

2.4 The Role of Green Behaviour in The Workplace

Green Behaviour provides information on a sustainable work environment. Employees can reduce the negative impact on the practical use of energy consumption. Environmentally friendly practices improve a company's reputation in the eyes of the public [20]. Green behavior in the company must be maintained to become an environmentally friendly habit for employees and help them achieve optimal performance. Carrying out tasks based on green behavior is part of routine daily activities during working hours [66]. Green behavior must be a personal choice and of one's own will, not coercion from superiors. Green behavior is a natural action of individuals to protect and preserve the environment daily [21].

Three leading indicators focus on understanding and measuring Green Behavior: environmental awareness, environmentally friendly purchasing behavior, and perceived benefits. Environmental awareness is the state of an individual's awareness of the impact of every activity they do. The main factor supporting consumers' choice to buy pro-environmental products is environmental awareness [67]. A vital concern about environmental awareness drives the reaction to alleviating environmental issues. The level of environmental awareness reflects values and attitudes that support achieving sustainable development goals within the company. This awareness is the basis for forming consistent Green Behavior [20].

An eco-friendly purchase is a decision from the user to have a product that cares about the environment. The growing preference of consumers to use environmentally friendly products is accommodated by the industry by creating products that are recyclable and do not pollute the environment [66]. Green purchasing shows a commitment to supporting the growth of green markets and the development of business models oriented towards environmental responsibility [68]. The subjectivity and knowledge of customers greatly influence the positive attitude shown by the purchase of environmentally friendly products. The consumption of green products has a close relationship with low-carbon behavior in supporting the success of public policies. The industry is forced to adapt to demand and support global sustainability [69].

Receiving benefits directly is an aspect of supporting efforts to implement environmentally friendly activities. Every individual who feels the benefits directly tends to be more motivated to carry out activities repeatedly and has the potential to set an example for others to take action [70]. Direct and indirect benefits can be illustrated in the Green Jobs implementation process. The direct benefits for the company include aspects of economic benefits. Indirect benefits are related to environmental benefits, economic promotion benefits, risk abandonment benefits, and company service improvement benefits [71].

These benefits also strengthen the belief that every individual action can significantly impact the environment, so it is expected to encourage more people to engage in environmentally friendly practices. Based on the above arguments, we propose that:

H6. Green Jobs have a positive and significant effect on Green Behavior.

2.5 Competency-Based Workforce Development Strategy in the Green Industry Era

Workforce Development is designed to provide increased skills and knowledge in Green Jobs. Competency-based workforce training supports the progress of environmentally friendly industries [72]. The need for environmentally friendly workforce development is carried out to ensure competence in following industry needs. Companies need a workforce with skills based on sustainable business activities [73]. Candidates must be ready to form a quality and environmentally friendly workforce when they enter high school. Schools must be actively involved in educating their students about the prospects of Green Jobs in the future because schools have an important role in producing a workforce with environmentally based skills [74]. Educational institutions can design training and development programs that target specific competencies. In addition, developing green industry-based competencies should include non-technical skills such as sustainability project management, effective communication about environmentally friendly practices, and the ability to adapt to changing environmental regulations [75].

Three leading indicators focus on understanding and measuring Workforce Development: competency development, basic training and early career development, quality assurance, and academic capacity. Competency development is the first indicator of improving workers' skills and knowledge. Competency development is necessary because it can improve workers' knowledge, performance, and skills to meet increasingly complex job demands [76]. This development includes various formal and informal training forms designed to strengthen workers' technical and non-technical abilities. With continuously updated competencies with this training, the workforce becomes more adaptive and ready to face changes in the industry, thereby increasing organizational productivity and efficiency [77].

Basic training and early career development are the second indicators emphasizing the importance of providing a solid foundation for new workers to enter the workforce. This introductory training includes an introduction to industry standards, safe work practices, and professional ethical values [78]. In addition, early career development guides young workers in planning and developing career paths that match their potential and aspirations. This step is critical to ensure that workers have a solid foundation and a clear perspective on the future of their careers [79]. Quality assurance is the third indicator of continuous monitoring and evaluation of training and development programs. Quality assurance must ensure that the training provided is interesting and relevant to industry needs [80]. In addition, Quality assurance also includes periodic evaluation of worker performance to ensure that it continues to develop according to established standards. Through strict quality assurance, organizations can monitor worker performance to ensure that investments in Workforce Development provide optimal results [81].

Academic capacity is the fourth indicator that reflects the relationship between education and industry needs. Academic capacity includes the ability of educational institutions to provide courses that align with the labor market's needs and collaborate with industry to provide practical experience for students [82]. Strong academic capacity ensures graduates are ready to enter the workforce with relevant and up-to-date skills [83]. Workforce Development can be done holistically to ensure that each individual has the skills necessary for the current job. Workforce Development to create a competitive, productive, and competitive workforce [84]. Based on the above arguments, we propose that:

- H7a. Workforce Development plays a moderating role in Green Jobs towards Environmental Literacy.
- H7b. Workforce Development plays a moderating role in Green Jobs towards Green Skills.
- H7c. Workforce Development plays a moderation role in Green Jobs against Green Behaviour.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design uses quantitative and qualitative approaches. This study involves collecting data through a survey of high school students. The survey will be used to measure the level of Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behavior that they have done. In addition, they are conducting in-depth interviews with teachers and school administrators. This is done to understand how the environmentally focused Workforce Development program is implemented and integrated into the curriculum. After all the data is collected, the next stage will be carried out, namely analysis. Quantitative data will be analyzed using statistical techniques to measure and identify the relationship between measured variables. Meanwhile, qualitative data enriches contextual understanding and provides in-depth insights into implementing environmentally friendly practices in schools.

3.2 Target Population

The target population in this study was high school students from several schools in East Java, with a total of 125 students. The students selected were based on the criteria of students experiencing educational crises where knowledge, skills, and behavior related to the environment could be formed effectively. The chosen population will explore how literacy, green skills, and student behavior can be influenced and developed to support the creation of future sustainable and environmentally friendly jobs.

3.3 Sampling

The data collection method in this study will use the Random Sampling Technique. The purpose of this technique is to ensure the results are representative of the samples taken. In its implementation, this technique will involve high school students randomly selected from a wider population so that each member of the population has an equal chance of

being selected as a respondent. Furthermore, a survey will be conducted on the selected respondents. This aims to measure environmental literacy, green skills, and student behavior.

The questionnaire will include closed questions designed to produce objective data so that the results can be analyzed statistically. In addition to conducting a survey, in-depth interviews will be conducted with several respondents who have been randomly selected. This interview aims to obtain data regarding a deeper understanding of their views and experiences regarding school green practices, including environmental literacy and green skills. This approach is used to ensure that the data used truly reflects the perspectives and actual conditions in the field.

3.4 Data Collection

This study uses a questionnaire with Likert scale items to measure respondent sentiment. A set of items with a Likert scale in a survey measures aspects that conventional techniques cannot measure. The scale functions to change individual subjectivity into a more consistent quantitative measurement. The Likert scale that will be used has a range of values from 1 to 5, where the number 1 will represent the statement "strongly disagree," and 5 represents the statement "strongly agree." Answers that agree or disagree based on the scale will make it easier for participants to answer questions, resulting in less response burden during the survey. Respondents will be asked to fill out a prepared questionnaire and provide their assessment of the statements submitted. The statements submitted include the environmental literacy level, green skills, and green behavior in everyday life. Examples of statements that might be asked in the questionnaire include "I feel I have enough knowledge about environmental issues" or "I have implemented environmentally friendly practices in my daily life." Using this Likert scale will make it easier for researchers to get a clearer picture of respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and level of awareness regarding the importance of green jobs and the development of relevant environmentally-based skills among school students. The data generated from this questionnaire will then be subjected to further analysis to understand patterns and trends among respondents.

3.5 Measurement

The Survey Focus in this study is divided into three parts: the role of environmental literacy, green skills, and green behavior. First is environmental literacy. In this section, respondents will fill out a survey containing environmental issues, such as climate change, resource conservation, and the impact of pollution, to find out how they assess their knowledge of these issues [43]. Second, green skills will be used to evaluate respondents' technical and non-technical abilities to implement green practices in the school environment and everyday life [85]. In this second section, respondents will be asked to assess how well they have mastered skills such as recycling, processing, reducing waste, and efficiently using unnecessary energy [54]. Third, it focuses on Green Behavior. At this stage, respondents are asked to reflect on their habits in adopting actions that support sustainability, such as saving water, reducing plastic use, and participating in environmental activities [20]. This survey is designed to provide

comprehensive insights into how school students understand, develop, and apply environmentally friendly concepts and practices.

3.6 Analysis Methods

The interaction between observable and latent variables can be explored using structural equation modeling with the partial least squares method (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM uses an approach that combines factor analysis and regression to model the relationship between latent variables that cannot be measured conventionally with observable variables [86]. This will make it easier for researchers to evaluate environmental literacy, green skills, and green behaviors interacting and influencing the development of an environmentally friendly workforce among students in the school environment [87]. In addition, it makes it easier to identify pathways of influence that have a significant impact, makes it easier to evaluate the strength of the relationship between variables, and test the overall theoretical model [88]. This approach will provide deep insight into the complex dynamics between factors that influence students' readiness to participate in jobs that support environmental sustainability in the future.

4. RESULT

4.1 Common method bias

In research, the possibility of general method bias is taken seriously. This bias can occur when independent and dependent variables are measured using the same approach, potentially obscuring the results and giving the impression that a stronger or weaker relationship exists between the variables. This study uses the inner and outer variance inflation factor (VIF) test, which is an indicator used to detect the presence of multicollinearity between variables in the model. It is expected to be able to identify and overcome this standard method bias. In this test, a high VIF value indicates a strong correlation between the variables, which can cause bias. By conducting the Inner and Outer VIF tests, researchers can evaluate and minimize the impact of bias of standard methods, thus ensuring that the study results are more valid and reliable. This approach helps maintain the integrity of the analysis. It provides a more accurate picture of the relationship between Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, Green Behaviour, and Workforce Development among school students. The outer (inner) VIF value of each exogenous construct ranges from (1,000 – 2,703) < criterion 3.3.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

The data in the study showed that the respondents who participated in this study involved 125 students, most of whom were female respondents (60%). Most respondents came from public schools (61.6%) and grade 3 (60%). Most of the students lived in urban areas (78.4%). The most widely followed majors were Natural Sciences (40.8%), followed by Social Sciences (32%), Language (14.4%), and finally Religion (12.8%). These data provide an overview of the demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in this study, reflecting the diversity of educational backgrounds and places of residence.

4.3 Measurement model

4.3.1 Reliability and Convergent Validity

Table 1: Inner model VIF

Construction	Green Job	Workforce Development	Criteria (<3.3)
Green Job			Yes
Environmental Literacy	1.000	1.000	Yes
Green Skills	1.000	1.000	Yes
Green Behaviour	1.000	1.000	Yes
Workforce Development	2.703		Yes

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) are methods used to test the reliability and validity of the variables used. AVE will measure how much influence the latent variable can have on the variance of its indicators. A high AVE value indicates that the measured construct has good convergence validity. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR) are methods used to test the reliability and validity of the variables used. AVE will measure how much influence the latent variable can have on the variance of its indicators. A high AVE value indicates that the measured construct has good convergence validity. This means that most of the information contained in the indicator can be accommodated in the latent variables being measured [89].

Meanwhile, the method that will be used to measure the internal consistency of the variables is CR. CR is used to measure the same construct to ensure that the indicators can provide reliable and consistent results [90]. The AVE value is more than 0.5, while the CR value is higher than the recommended threshold of 0.70. The value of AVE having a larger square root will have a value of validity of the crime. According to the results, the existing construct value has good validity, significance, consistency, and discrimination. In addition, the loading rate of factors in the range of 0.60-0.90 can be categorized well. Cron-bach's alpha value ranges from 0.811 to 0.911. In addition, the AVE value between 0.644 and 0.790 based on the existing data can be categorized as accepted research results [60].

4.3.2 Discriminant Validity

Establishing construct validity is a very important step in research. Establishing a construct can ensure that each concept measured truly reflects the intended construct and is different from other constructs. Measurement instruments referred to in construct validity, such as research instruments or questionnaires, can measure certain aspects of the construct being investigated. The methods used include the Hetrotriate-Monotriant ratio (HTMT) test, the Fornell-Larcker criterion, and cross-loading to ensure that the different constructs are identified separately and do not affect each other. By ensuring the validity of the construct, the researcher can confirm that the results obtained accurately represent each aspect being studied and provide a clear picture of the relationship between the variables in this study when the HTMT value is above the recommended cut-off point of 0.75-0.90 for structural models with components that are conceptually relatively identical [91]. The results of the validity test of the research discrimination can be found through the following Tables 4–6:

Table 2: Construct reliability and convergent validity

lbri'	Unit	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	(AVE)
Green Job (X1)	Quality of the Work Environment (X1.1)	0.938	0.852	0.853	0.901	0.694
	Gender Equality (X1.2)	0.935	0.811	0.812	0.888	0.726
	Career Sustainability (X1.3)	0.960	0.850	0.855	0.899	0.690
	Work Culture (X1.4)	0.972	0.875	0.877	0.915	0.729
Environmental Literacy (Y1)	Environmental values (Y1.1)	0.882	0.873	0.873	0.913	0.724
	Environmental responsibility (Y1.2)	0.845	0.847	0.847	0.908	0.766
	Perception of environmental problems (Y1.3)	0.844	0.862	0.862	0.916	0.784
Green Skills (Y2)	Idea & knowledge management (Y2.1)	0.885	0.911	0.912	0.938	0.790
	Develop & drive strategy (Y2.2)	0.869	0.904	0.904	0.933	0.776
	Innovative sustainability (Y2.3)	0.885	0.840	0.842	0.903	0.757
	Sustainable & Innovative Energy Management (Y2.4)	0.902	0.887	0.888	0.922	0.747
Green Behaviour (Y3)	Environmental awareness (Y3.1)	0.880	0.878	0.880	0.917	0.733
	Eco-Friendly Purchasing Behavior (Y3.2)	0.900	0.891	0.892	0.924	0.754
	Benefits felt (Y3.3)	0.884	0.905	0.906	0.934	0.779
Workforce Development (Z1)	Competency development (Z1.1)	0.796	0.882	0.884	0.919	0.739
	Basic training and Early career development (Z1.2)	0.729	0.827	0.827	0.885	0.659
	Quality assurance (Z1.3)	0.695	0.826	0.828	0.885	0.658
	Academic capacity (Z1.4)	0.692	0.816	0.816	0.879	0.644

4.3.3 Model fit

In the study, it is essential to understand that the PLS-SEM (Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling) technique is designed to maximize the variance described in the model. Since the primary purpose of PLS-SEM is to improve the prediction and interpretation of variance, the literature warns against relying too much on the global fit model index as the only measure of model success. The global fit model index often used in traditional SEM techniques is the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) or Comparative Fit Index (CFI), which aims to assess how well the model fits the data. PLS-SEM primarily focuses on maximizing explained variance and construct validity, so the resulting index may not fully reflect the quality of the model. Therefore, it is very important to consider other

aspects, such as construct validity, reliability, and the strength of the relationship between variables, when assessing the PLS-SEM model to ensure more comprehensive and valid research results. The study results in Table 7 provide information related to the R² value of 0.881 and 0.631 in the Green Job and Environmental Literacy construct variables, which explains that the construct is reasonable. The R-squared value of the Green Job variable is 88.1%, which means that the independent variable directly influences it, and the residual value is likely to be highly respected by other variables outside the scope of the study. In addition, the Environmental Literacy variable was influenced by 63.1% in this study. Based on the q-square calculation above, it can be stated that the predictive relevance model reaches 98.5% and 86.2%, indicating that the analysis has appropriate predictive relevance [90].

4.4 Structural model

Structural analysis is a further stage after the measurement model. This stage focuses on a deeper understanding of the relationship between variables in the model, where this focus has shifted from the previous focus, namely the validity and reliability of variable measurement. The purpose of this structural analysis is very complex, starting from identifying and then evaluating the relationship path between other variables, including environmental literacy, green skills, and green behavior. In addition, it wants to know the impact of developing an environmentally friendly workforce. Using the PLS-SEM technique, researchers can evaluate the strength and direction of the relationship between variables and test hypotheses regarding the influence of independent variables on dependent variables.

The data presented in the table above illustrates the statistical analysis results regarding the relationship between Green Jobs and three main variables, namely Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behavior, as well as their influence on Workforce Development. Each relationship or hypothesis is measured based on the original sample, standard deviation, t-statistic, p-value, and whether or not the hypothesis is supported.

The first hypothesis (H1) tests the effect of Green Jobs on Environmental Literacy. The results of the study indicate that the hypothesis is significantly supported. The result of the relationship coefficient is 0.713, with a standard deviation of 0.069. The t-statistic value is 10.276, and the p-value is 0.000. The second hypothesis (H2) assesses the relationship between Green Jobs and Green Skills. This study shows a high level of significance. The result of the relationship coefficient is 0.742, with a standard deviation of 0.052. The t-statistic value is 14.216, and the p-value is 0.000.

The third hypothesis (H3) examines the influence of Green Jobs on Green Behavior. The study results showed that individuals involved in Green Jobs tend to develop more environmentally friendly behavior where the coefficient value is 0.669 with a standard deviation of 0.070. At the same time, the t-statistic value obtained in the study was 9.544 with a p-value of 0.000. The fourth hypothesis (H4) examines the influence of the relationship between Workforce Development and Environmental Literacy. This study's results indicate a significant influence, but not as big as the direct influence of Green Jobs. The result of the coefficient value of the relationship found was 0.245, with a standard

deviation of 0.075. The t-statistic value is 3.250, and the p-value is 0.001. The fifth hypothesis (H5) examines the impact of Workforce Development on Green Skills. The results of the study show that development influences green skills. The result of the coefficient value is 0.253, with a standard deviation of 0.051. The t-statistic value is 4.949 with a p-value of 0.000. The sixth hypothesis (H6) tests the relationship between Workforce Development and Environmentally Friendly Behavior. The results of the study indicate that there is a significant influence. The result of the coefficient value is 0.320, with a standard deviation of 0.069. The t-statistic value is 4.642, with a p-value of 0.000.

Table 3: Discriminant validity (Fornell-Larker criteria)

Variable	X1	Y1	Y2	Y3	Z1
Green Job	0.802				
Environmental Literacy	0.907	0.823			
Green Skills	0.943	0.938	0.822		
Green Behaviour	0.924	0.918	0.953	0.835	
Workforce Development	0.794	0.811	0.843	0.852	0.757

Table 4: Discriminant validity (cross-loading)

Items	X1	Y1	Y2	Y3	Z1	VIF
X1.1	0.764	0.697	0.715	0.694	0.657	2.143
X1.2	0.790	0.753	0.753	0.743	0.620	2.003
X1.3	0.759	0.678	0.737	0.733	0.604	1.828
X1.4	0.835	0.721	0.744	0.742	0.651	2.852
Y1.1	0.747	0.786	0.736	0.750	0.733	2.133
Y1.2	0.748	0.830	0.770	0.752	0.675	2.107
Y1.3	0.728	0.844	0.783	0.746	0.610	2.515
Y2.1	0.805	0.790	0.864	0.781	0.675	2.822
Y2.2	0.775	0.779	0.830	0.742	0.652	2.214
Y2.3	0.739	0.719	0.766	0.780	0.669	1.904
Y2.4	0.759	0.771	0.797	0.805	0.736	2.305
Y3.1	0.723	0.760	0.775	0.814	0.680	2.317
Y3.2	0.756	0.778	0.785	0.849	0.790	2.470
Y3.3	0.795	0.777	0.817	0.863	0.733	2.776
Z1.1	0.710	0.744	0.784	0.775	0.818	2.504
Z1.2	0.670	0.666	0.659	0.711	0.786	2.093
Z1.3	0.579	0.637	0.617	0.654	0.772	2.284
Z1.4	0.577	0.582	0.606	0.595	0.739	1.804

Table 5: Discriminant validity (HTMT)

Variable	X1	Y1	Y2	Y3	Z1
Green Job					
Environmental Literacy	0.952				
Green Skills	0.980	0.981			
Green Behaviour	0.963	0.963	0.990		
Workforce Development	0.829	0.851	0.877	0.888	

Table 6: Coefficient of determination (R²), predictive relevance (Q²), and effect size (F₂)

Exogenous Construction	F ₂	Z ₁	(R ²)	R ² Adjusted	(Q ²)
	X1	Z1			
Green Job			0.881	0.880	0.985
Environmental Literacy	9.829		0.631	0.628	0.862
Green Skills	8.804	7.107			
Green Behaviour	8.884	17.467			
Workforce Development	0.273	5.011			

Table 7: Hypothesis test (direct effect)

Hypothesis	Relationship	Original Sample	St. Dev	t- Statistics	P- Values	Support?
H1.	Green Jobs -) Environmental Literacy	0.713	0.069	10.276	0.000	Yes
H2.	Green Jobs -) Green Skills	0.742	0.052	14.216	0.000	Yes
H3.	Green Jobs -) Green Behaviour	0.669	0.070	9.544	0.000	Yes
H4.	Workforce Development -) Environmental Literacy	0.245	0.075	3.250	0.001	Yes
H5.	Green Jobs -) Green Skills	0.253	0.051	4.949	0.000	Yes
H6.	Green Jobs -) Green Behaviour.	0.320	0.069	4.642	0.000	Yes
H7.a	Workforce Development -) Green Jobs -) Environmental Literacy	0.194	0.065	2.979	0.003	Yes
H7.b	Workforce Development -) Green Jobs -) Green Skills	0.201	0.046	4.419	0.000	Yes
H7.c	Workforce Development -) Green Jobs -) Green Behaviour.	0.254	0.064	3.987	0.000	Yes

4.5 Mediation Effect

The H7.a hypothesis related to Workforce Development affects Environmental Literacy through Green Jobs. The results showed an Original Sample value of 0.194 with a t-statistics value of 2.979 and a p-value of 0.003, which means that this relationship is significant and supported by data. The H7.b hypothesis related to Workforce Development affects Green Skills through Green Jobs. The Original Sample value of

0.201 with t-statistics of 4.419 and p-value of 0.000 shows a very significant relationship. The H7.c hypothesis related to Workforce Development affects Green Behavior through Green Jobs. The results showed an Original Sample value of 0.254 with t-statistics of 3.987 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a significant relationship

5. DISCUSSION

This study further turns to the fact that green jobs in the school environment significantly influence the improvement of environmental literacy, green skills, and green behavior through workforce development. In addition, the role of Workforce Development as a mediator who provides information on the importance of its application in the school environment to educate the prospects of Green Jobs in the future era.

The first findings in H1 showed that work that focused on environmental aspects significantly improved Environmental Literacy in individuals. This implies that an environmentally friendly understanding of the implementation of recycling is positively related to the increase in the probability and number of green jobs in several European companies [11]. Knowledge of Green Jobs opens up 2 million new jobs in Europe and the United States alone in the transition to green energy use [10]. This research contradicts the finding that Green Jobs are still unfamiliar to some people, so it is not easy to provide an understanding of Environmental Literacy to marginalized people in supporting the energy transition [92].

The second finding in H2 shows that eco-friendly jobs strongly influence improving individual skills in eco-friendly practices. Other findings suggest that technical skills are essential to fossil fuel jobs, and extensive service-oriented and management skills support jobs in the green energy sector [24]. Green Skills are also aligned with Industry 4.0 skills) that support green governance [93]. However, determining skills in the green sector still overlaps the skills needed and the existing skill requirements [54].

The third finding in H3 indicates that individuals involved in Green Jobs tend to develop more environmentally friendly behaviors. A similar study on 508 employees in the hospitality industry showed the direct impact of environmental attitudes on ecosystem behavior and customer service [94]. Green work behavior significantly impacts job performance in Viet Nam's public sector [95]. Three hundred bank employees have extrical motivations that give rise to green behavior in the customer service process in the green finance industry [22].

The fourth finding in H4 shows that Workforce Development programs can improve Environmental Literacy but have a more negligible impact than Green Jobs. Other research shows that transferring Environmental Literacy knowledge in green Workforce Development can foster green-based advanced technology ideas [73]. Similar findings show that pharmaceutical workforce training programs in Commonwealth countries can increase the capacity of pharmaceutical workers and Environmental Literacy towards herbal medicines [72]. Partnerships with educational institutions are needed for local Environmental Literacy-based Workforce Development in Georgia's manufacturing industry [96].

The fifth finding in H5 shows that Workforce Development programs can improve individual Green Skills. Existing research shows that final-year airline students show positive results in workforce training with a non-technical skills approach and green skills career options [79]. In addition, transforming the nursing workforce in Angola uses the path of professional differentiation through green skills [75]. The training and development role of green construction employees in the United Kingdom can reduce the negative impact of COVID-19 accompanied by the addition of green skills [97].

The sixth finding in H6 shows that Workforce Development has shaped Green Behaviour. Existing research shows that workforce training related to green behavior can positively impact individual purchasing [20]. Employees' green behavior in sustainable leadership guidance contributes to employee responsibility and motivation to implement environmentally friendly regulations [98]. Another study shows a "shared vision of green" as an intermediary in shaping green behaviors in worker roles and job desks in MBA executive program students [25].

The seventh finding on H7a shows that improvements in Workforce Development positively affect Environmental Literacy, with Green Jobs as the mediator. Another study demonstrates the use of an applied approach in the TEC21 Education Model of the Tecnológico de Monterrey as a means of training students to delve into cutting-edge technologies and the learning of Environmental Literacy in the professional world [76]. Activity-Based training (ABT) can provide a quality assurance process for participants in understanding Environmental Literacy in an organization [81]. H7b indicates that when Workforce Development is improved, there is a significant increase in Green Skills in Green Jobs. Another finding that supports this study is on-the-go training for non-routine tasks with Prescriptive Analytics, which contributes to the evolution of the worker training paradigm from the perspective of environmentally oriented production systems [99]. Similar results in H7c show that Workforce Development affects skills and Environmental Literacy and significantly impacts Green Behaviour in Green Jobs. Other research indicates that green practices, marketing orientation, and investment significantly impact a company's economic performance [90]. Other findings show that green-based training practices held by human resource management can affect employee involvement in supporting green banking company programs [89].

6. CONCLUSION

This research was conducted to answer the question of how Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behaviour can play a role in creating a workforce that is ready to support Green Jobs among school students. Based on the findings obtained, this study successfully shows that Workforce Development significantly influences the creation of Green Jobs, increasing Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behaviour among students. These findings reinforce the argument that investment in Workforce Development improves workforce readiness and contributes to overall environmental sustainability. This study's main findings show a close relationship between Workforce Development and variables such as Environmental Literacy, Green Skills, and Green Behaviour. The influence of Workforce Development on Environmental Literacy

(influence value 0.194, $p < 0.05$), Green Skills (0.201, $p < 0.001$), and Green Behaviour (0.254, $p < 0.001$) shows that the Workforce Development factor plays an essential role in mediating these achievements. In other words, when the workforce is given adequate training and self-competence development, it will positively impact the company, where they tend to support and actively engage in environmentally friendly practices.

The implications of these findings for education and workforce training are significant. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating environmental literacy and green skills into the education curriculum, especially at the secondary school level. After being piloted, the results of this study were able to encourage educational institutions to adopt a holistic approach to preparing and developing a workforce that is not only technically competent but also aware of and committed to environmental sustainability. In addition, these findings provide theoretical contributions by enriching the literature on the importance of workforce development in supporting the transition to a green economy and how these variables are interrelated.

In general, this research has contributed significantly. However, some limitations can still be improved in further research. First, this study uses a quantitative approach, with the sample still limited to high school students, who may not be the entire population. In addition, the Single measurement approach used in the independent and dependent variables can cause common method bias. So, for further research, it is recommended to use a more complete method, such as a mixed method or a longitudinal approach, to explore the dynamics of the variables. In addition, it is also recommended that the sample be expanded to provide a more comprehensive picture of how the implementation of workforce development and green jobs influence each other in various contexts.

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Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

Conflict Of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare relevant to this article's content.

Ethics Declarations

Before data collection, participants were informed that their participation in this non-experimental study was completely voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time and for any reason without penalty or loss of benefits to which they were entitled, if any. They were also informed that no known risks were associated with participating in the study. Furthermore, their surveys would be kept confidential, and the data collected would not contain any information that could be used to identify school students. All participants had voluntarily agreed to participate. The ethics committee that reviewed this study was Universitas Negeri Malang.

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